

Emotional Intelligence and Leadership Profiles among Students' Representative Council of Malaysian Public Universities

R. A. Harun, N. M. Ishak, N. Yusoff, S. Amat

Abstract—This quantitative research is aimed to identify the level of leadership quality and emotional intelligence for members of Students' Representatives Council (SRC) of Malaysian Public Universities (MPU). The variables include the leadership quality and emotional quotient (EQ). 238 SRC members in MPU were selected as subjects of the study. Data were collected using two instruments i.e. Malaysian Emotional Quotient Inventory (MEQI) and Ayu-Noriah Leadership Audit Trail Inventory (Ayu-Noriah, LATI). Data were analyzed using descriptive (mean and percentage). Research findings showed that the subjects scored highly in four out of five EQ domains (Self-Regulations, Self-Motivation, Empathy and Social Skills). However, the subjects scored medium to low in Self-Awareness. Analysis on the sub domains (a total of 28 sub domains) showed that the subjects scored high in 17 sub domains for EQ, whilst another 11 were at medium level. The overall analysis indicates that the subjects have high level of EQ. Findings on their leadership qualities showed that they obtained high scores in all seven factors that were measured i.e. Strategy and Leadership Model, Recruit, Review Performance and Honor, Deploy Strategically, Developing, Engage and Retain and Built HR Capabilities/Line Ownership. The overall score for leadership qualities was found to be high.

Keywords—Emotional intelligence, leadership, students.

I. INTRODUCTION

UNIVERSITY plays a vital role in achieving the goal of producing knowledgeable and highly skilled human capital that is very much needed in the job market nowadays. This goal requires university to produce excellent graduates, which are able to fulfill the needs and hopes of the country; not only at being knowledgeable and able to master their disciplines but also to possess specific skills such as emotional intelligence and leadership, as well as adapting well in the job market. "University plays an integral role to produce graduates that are not only academically excellent, but talented graduates that have skills that is needed in this 21st century" [12]. The 4C skills are:

A. Critical thinking & problem solving;

- B. Effective communication;
- C. Collaboration & team building;
- D. Creativity & innovation.

According to [14] soft skill is a sociological term that refers to the EQ of an individual, that is related to his or her characteristics or personality traits, skills to socialize, communicates, language proficiency in written or verbal form, positive habits or behavior, sociability and optimism in life and their social circles. Soft skills are skills required by students alongside their academic field in order to become more successful and excellent as practitioners in their academic field, work and life.

"Emotional intelligence is a key subject in determining academic achievement, domestic happiness and physical health" [13]. On the other hand, students with better emotional intelligence have better grades in contrast to students who are intellectually gifted but not emotionally competent [10]. Possessing intellectual intelligence allows students to manage their feelings and develop strong self-concept. Students possessing high level of emotional intelligence are better at controlling their emotions, confident, affable, easily approached and likeable by their peers, teachers and members of society around them. Therefore, realizing the influential importance of emotional intelligence, many studies related to it have been conducted.

Most researchers agree that there is a positive correlation between emotional intelligence and effective leadership [15]. In general, emotional intelligence is not only essential to individual success in an organization, but emotional intelligence becomes a lot more imperative when the individual rises to become an organization leader [1].

A Leader should equip themselves with emotional competency skills because it would help them in making better decisions in performing their tasks and also to enhance the achievement of the organization [4]. Accordingly, the study on the level of emotional intelligence and leadership among the Students' Representative Council of MPU should be carried out in order to improve their leadership qualities. This is because emotional intelligence is able to assist Students' Representative Council of MPU to identify and control self-emotion and also other people, motivate themselves, manage their emotions, and manage their relationship with other people as well.

II. CONCEPTS OF EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE

"Emotional intelligence as the ability to control and

Harun, R. A. is Assistant Registrar with the National University of Malaysia Bangi Selangor Malaysia (e-mail: ayu77@ukm.edu.my).

Ishak, N. M. was with the Faculty of Education, National University of Malaysia Bangi Selangor Malaysia. She is now Director of PERMATAPintar National Gifted Centre (e-mail: norwmu@ukm.edu.my).

Yusoff, N. is Science Officer with the School of Environmental Science and Natural Resources, National University of Malaysia Bangi Selangor Malaysia (e-mail: nasirudin@ukm.edu.my).

Amat, S. is Head of Department with the Faculty of Education, National University of Malaysia Bangi Selangor Malaysia (e-mail: sallahba@ukm.edu.my).

organize oneself and other people from the aspects of feelings, emotions, and behavior” [2]. It is also the action and ingenuity to modify behavior according to time and situation. He also suggested that “an individual evaluation is not only based on his or her intellectual ability (IQ), but more importantly, the EQ that he or she possesses”. The definition offered by [3] quoted above contains five domains in emotional intelligence as shown in Fig. 1:

Fig. 1 Emotional Intelligence Model by Daniel Goleman

Goleman’s EQ model has categorized emotional intelligence into five emotional intelligence factors, which are self-awareness, self-regulation, self-motivation, empathy and social skills. This model has been developed further by identifying few existing domains. Goleman has categorized emotional intelligence into two key parts, which are:

A. Personal Competence

Personal competence indicates how an individual is able to manage and control his or herself in personal life and also, in the working sphere. Personal competence comprises of three domains, which are self-awareness, self-regulation and self-motivation. Self-awareness is the ability to understand internal situation, choice, resources and intuition of an individual. The self-awareness domain contains three sub-domains, which are emotional awareness, accurate self-evaluation and self-confidence. Self-regulation is a person’s ability to manage internal situation, instinct and resources. There are five sub-domains self-regulation, which are self-control, trustworthiness, conscientiousness, adaptability and innovativeness. On the other hand, self-motivation refers to the emotional tendency in guiding or facilitating an individual to achieve a particular goal. It comprises of four sub-domains, which are achievement drive, commitment, initiative and lastly, optimism.

B. Social Competence

Social competence is the skills to establish relationship or friendship with other people, communication skills, negotiating, and the ability to solve problems related to their relationship with other people. This social competence comprises of two domains that are empathy and social skills. Empathy is defined as being aware of other people’s feelings, needs and problems. It has five sub-domains, which are understand others, developing other people’s potential, service-orientation, leveraging diversity and political awareness. Social skills on the other hand are the skills to

generate required responses from other people. There are eight sub-domains in social skills, which are influence, communication, conflict management, leadership, change catalyst, building bonds, collaboration and cooperation.

III. CONCEPTS OF LEADERSHIP

There are many meanings and definitions of leadership. According to [6], leadership is an effort in influencing between leaders and their followers. The leadership process often displays a two-way influence ties and its main purpose is to achieve mutual goals. Effective leaders show high commitment and encouragement through their appearance as excellent models stemming from their consistent, open and exhibiting high regards towards exemplary morals. Traits shown shall contribute to strength, confidence and inspiration among their subordinates.

The scope of this research emphasized the seven leadership frameworks in The Orange Book: Strengthening Leadership Development prepared in the Malaysia Government-Linked Company (GLC) Transformation Program [9]. This orange book is prepared as a guide in establishing and managing leaders and other human capital. Its objective is to develop a guideline that contains best practices to attract individuals with high potentials. The effort to attract, develop and retain talented individuals is very critical in any organization. The framework is shown in Fig. 2:

Fig. 2 Leadership Development Framework in The Orange Book: Strengthening Leadership Development

There are seven leadership frameworks proposed in the orange book which has set the ground for this research discussion. Each of the seven items consists of three essential elements utilized in action evaluation, which are policy, process and practice, mind-sets and results. The orange book leadership framework is chosen by the researcher because it is an initiative among the GLC to increase their approach in human capital management and to close the gap between GLC

and the best private companies in Malaysia and comparable companies at the international level. This framework is capable to build and manage leaders and young human capital of Public University students that shall inherit the nation leadership in the future.

IV. RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The research answers two research questions, which are:

- A. What is the emotional intelligence profile of the Students' Representative Council of MPU?
- B. What is the leadership profile of the Students' Representative Council of MPU?

V. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

A. Research Population and Sample

The ten public universities have been selected randomly to homogeneously represent five zones are listed in the Table I:

TABLE I
STUDENT REPRESENTATIVE COUNCIL MALAYSIA PROFILE BY ZONES

Zone	Public Universities	Frequency	%
Kelang Valley	National Defenses Universities Malaysia	14	5.9
	National Islamic Universities Malaysia	21	8.8
South	Tun Hussein Onn Universities Malaysia	31	13.0
	Technical Universities Malaysia Melaka	25	10.5
East	Malaysia Kelantan Universities	15	6.3
	Malaysia Pahang Universities	27	11.3
North	Malaysia Perlis Universities	30	12.6
	Utara Malaysia Universities	34	14.3
Non Peninsular	Malaysia Sabah Universities	28	11.8
	Malaysia Sarawak Universities	13	5.5
Total		238	100

The members of Students' Representative Council 2015/2016 session in ten public universities in Malaysia have been chosen as the research sample. The total of research sample according to the public universities classified based on their zones are listed in Table I. 238 members of Student Representative Council of MPU have been selected as respondents for this research.

B. Research Instruments

The research has utilized only two instruments i.e. Emotional Intelligence Survey (Malaysian Emotional Quotient Inventory-National University of Malaysia MEQI-NUM), which is developed by a team of NUM researchers lead by Noriah Mohd Ishak, based on Goleman-Norrah Emotional Intelligence Model. The second survey adopted in this research is Noriah-Ayu LATI leadership survey of the adult version that has been modified from the Leadership Model of Leadership Development Audit in the Orange Book. The Noriah-Ayu LATI leadership survey, LATI is used for the first time among Students' Representative Council of MPU.

VI. RESEARCH FINDINGS

A. Emotional Intelligence Profile

The overall percentage score and mean score for emotional

intelligence domain for Students' Representative Council of MPU are listed in Table II. For self-awareness domain, the mean score is 91.11 (78.55%), self-regulation 146.21 (81.23%), self-motivation 101.86 (81.28%), empathy 164.86 (80.42%) and social skills 145.37 (80.76%).

TABLE II
TOTAL PERCENTAGE AND MEAN SCORE OF EMOTION QUOTIENT DOMAIN

EQ Domain	Mean Score	Percentage (%)
Self-awareness	91.11	78.55
Self-regulation	146.21	81.23
Self-motivation	101.86	81.28
Empathy	164.86	80.42
Social skills	145.37	80.76
Total Mean	129.88	80.45

TABLE III
PERCENTAGE MEAN SCORE FOR EACH EQ DOMAIN

EQ Domain	Sub-Domain	%
Self-awareness	Emotional Awareness	71.99
	Accurate Self-evaluation	79.70
	Self-confident	78.41
	Honesty	79.77
	Self-control	78.22
Self-regulation	Trustworthiness	79.98
	Conscientiousness	76.99
	Innovativeness	82.35
	Achievement Motivation	81.10
Self-motivation	Commitment	81.38
	Initiative	82.13
	Optimism	80.88
Empathy	Understanding Others	75.28
	Helps Others	82.03
	Service Orientation	82.34
	Develop Potential of Others	82.61
	Political Awareness	80.91
Social skills	Leveraging Diversity	82.47
	Loving	83.16
	Influence Others	74.96
	Conflict Management	78.91
	Leadership	82.52
	Accelerant	81.72
	Build Relationships	81.27
	Collaboration	82.10
Teamwork	82.04	
	Communication	83.16
Average Percent Index Component		80.45

B. Leadership Profile

Leadership profile of Students' Representative Council of MPU is listed in Table IV. For the Leadership Strategy and Model, percentage score is 84.58%, Recruit 83.27%, Review Performance and Honor 83.25%, Deploy Strategically 84.95%, Developing 83.92%, Engage and Retain 83.99% and Built Human Resources (HR) Capabilities/Line Ownerships is 84.35%. The average mean score for the leadership of public universities student leaders is 43.19 while the average percentage score is 84.04%.

VII. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

This research will contribute further reference and literature in relation to emotional intelligence among Students' Representative Council of MPU. The research findings reflect the quality of emotional intelligence among Students' Representative Council of MPU. The sub-domain qualities of

emotional intelligence based on model is derived from percentage scores in a quantitative research. The interpretation of emotional intelligence index value is indicated according to [7] as in Table V.

TABLE IV
 MEAN AND PERCENTAGE SCORE FOR LEADERSHIP DOMAIN

Leadership Domain	Mean Score	%
Strategy & Leadership Model	43.98	84.58
Recruit	53.29	83.27
Review Performance & Honor	43.29	83.25
Deploy Strategically	47.18	84.95
Developing	43.64	83.92
Engage and Retain	43.68	83.99
Built HR Capabilities/ Line Ownerships	47.24	84.35
Average	43.19	84.04

TABLE V
 INTERPRETATION OF EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE VALUE

Percentage Value	Emotional Intelligence Index	Level	Interpretation
80 to 100		High	Shows that the emotional intelligence trait that exists in an individual is strength for him and should be fully utilized.
60 to 79		Medium	Shows that the emotional intelligence trait that should be located in an individual can be strength for him, but it should be located in the individual.
40 to 59		Low	Shows that the emotional intelligence trait required in an individual should be developed because this trait is found to be at a low level.
Less than 40		Very Low	Shows that the emotional trait required in an individual is at a very low level and it should be developed quickly.

Students' Representative Council of MPU are expected to achieve the average score of emotional intelligence more than 90% because as leader, they must possess personality strength in order to help in guiding fellow students. As student leaders, they are much occupied with university, faculty, and college activities respectively, up to a point where they may neglect their study. According to [10], student with higher emotional intelligence often achieve better grades than those who are intellectually gifted but not emotionally competent. Therefore, as student leaders they need to balance their co-curricular activities and their academic study.

The result analysis for overall emotional intelligence percentage of Students' Representative Council of MPU shows it is at a high level of 80.45%. For self-regulation, self-motivation, empathy and social skills domain of emotional intelligence displays high levels of competency. However, for self-awareness domain, it is at a moderate level, recorded at below 80%, which shows that the emotional intelligence trait that should be located in the individual may be a source of strength for the individual, but it has to be located in the individual. As student leaders are seen as role models, they should possess a high competency of more than 80% for each of the five emotional competence domains. Nonetheless, as leaders, it is desirable for them to achieve a higher score of 90% and above to differentiate them from the normal students.

This research finding on emotional intelligence components conflicts with the study done by [8] where the overall emotional intelligence index is recorded at a moderate level.

The analysis shows that Students' Representative Council of MPU exhibit high competency for all seven leadership components, which are leadership strategy and model, training, evaluating and recognizing, expanding, developing, engagement & retention, and compatibility with university management. The overall score for leadership component obtained by Students' Representative Council of MPU in this research is 84.04%. However, Students' Representative Council of MPU should have achieved higher leadership competency, which is more than 90% in order to differentiate their leadership competency with other students. This research finding differs from the research done by [11]. Her research found that from all seven leadership factors, only one component which is Leadership Strategy and Model is discovered to be high, while the other six components which are training, evaluating and recognizing, expanding, developing, engagement and retention and compatibility with university management indicates moderate competency.

The research carried out shows an interesting profile that can be used to explain the leadership development trait of the studied Students' Representative Council of MPU. The overall index of leadership development of the Student' Representative Council obtained is at a high level that is 84.13%. However, in that trait, there is factor that has decreased the leadership development index to a lower level, which is evaluating and recognizing factor. The policy, process and practice that are highlighted in the Orange Book stated that leaders should practice the culture of recognition and build relationship between rewards and achievement [9]. This is because, as leaders, they should appreciate existing leadership and the people being lead.

In a world full of intense competition, only students with high level of soft skills will be able to land jobs easily. "This gives the impression that education provided at the university is not in tune with the industrial needs" [16]. Therefore, engagement in co-curricular activities, may be able to nurture students that are balanced in their intellectuality, spirituality, physical, emotional and personality. Co-curricular activities also have a role in shaping the leadership personality among graduates and this idea is supported by [5], who asserts that co-curricular activities are organized with the intention to produce leaders among students.

REFERENCES

- [1] Dulewicz, V. & Higg, M. 2004. Can emotional intelligent be developed? *Journal of Human Resource Management* 15(1): pp 95-111.
- [2] Goleman, D. 1999. *Working with Emotional Intelligence*. New York: Bantam Books.
- [3] Goleman, D. 1995. *Emotional Intelligence: Why It Can Matter More Than IQ*. New York: Bantam Books.
- [4] Goleman, D., Boyatzis, R. 2001. *Primal Leadership: The Hidden Driver of Great Performance*. Harvard Bussiness Review.,42-51.
- [5] Hamzah, M.I.M, Ishak, N.M., Ariffin, S.R. & Amat, S. 2009. The Roles of Emotional Intelligence and Emotion Focused Solution: Developing Leadership Qualities among College Students. *The International Journal of Interdisciplinary Social Sciences*. 4(6): 187-199.
- [6] Hollander, E.P. 1993. Legitimacy, power and influence: A perspective

- on relational features of leadership. In M.M. Chemers & R. Ayman. *Leadership Theory and Research: Perspective and Directions*. pg. 29-48. San Diego: Academic Press.
- [7] Ishak, N.M., Ariffin, S.R., Mahmud, Z., Rahman, S. & Ali, M. 2001. *Performance and Emotional Intelligence: A Correlational Study Among Malaysian Adolescence*. Kertas kerja The Eight International Literacy & Education Research Network Conference on Learning. Speteses, Greece. 4-8 Julai 2010.
- [8] Ishak, N.M., Ahmad, S., Desa, K.M., & Abdullah, R.T. 2009. *Kepintaran Emosi Sebagai Faktor Peramal Pencapaian Akademik Pelajar IPTA: Implikasi Terhadap Kebolehpasaran*. Online: <http://journalarticle.ukm.my/2062/1/noriah-et-al-tiada-muka-surat.pdf>.
- [9] Malaysia. 2006. *The Orange Book: Strengthening Leadership Development*. Putrajaya Committee on GLC High Performance. Transformation Management Office. Prime Minister Department.
- [10] Maurice. 1999. *Quotes for Students All About Emotional Intelligence from Six Second*. <http://6seconds.org>. 12 Februari 1999.
- [11] Muda, T.E.A.T. 2015. *Kecerdasan Emosi, Kepimpinan Dan Kepuasan Kerja Dalam Kalangan Ketua Guru Bimbingan dan Kaunseling Sekolah Menengah*. Doctoral Philosophy Thesis Faculty of Education, National University of Malaysia.
- [12] Nordin, M.K. 2013. *Pengajian Tinggi Pemacu Daya Saing Malaysia*. Amanat Tahun Baharu 2013 Minister of Higher Education of Malaysia.
- [13] Pool, C.R. 1997. *Up with Emotional Health*. *Educational Leadership* 54(8): 12-14.
- [14] Ridhwan, A. 2013. *Pelajar Kita Masih Tumpul Kemahiran Insaniah*. *Berita Harian*, 16 Julai 2013.
- [15] Sosik, J.J., Avolio, B.J. & Jung, D.I. 2002. Beneath the mask: examining the relationship of self-presentation attributes and impression management to charismatic leadership. *Leadership Quarterly*. Vol. 3 No 3, pg 217-42.
- [16] Yusoff, M. 2006. *Penyediaan Graduan Untuk Pasaran Kerja Global*. In. *Halatuju Pengurusan Sumber Manusia dan Kerjaya*. Rashid, A.R.A., Hussin, S. & Othman, A.J. pg. 19-31. Kuala Lumpur: Utusan Publications.